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Report on D4.5: “Characterization of the EBL-written gratings”

Context of the task

Deliverable D4.5 “Grating characterization” is the final part of Task 4.4 “Grating characterization with synchrotron and FEL radiation” of Work Package 4. The prototype gratings are an essential outcome of WP4, showcasing the feasibility to produce high-quality blazed gratings by electron-beam lithography (EBL). The showcase is concluded by installing the gratings in existing X-ray spectrometers for the energy analysis of (fluorescence or scattered) X-rays and record spectral distributions obtained from exciting materials with synchrotron or FEL radiation.

The gratings were designed as described in the *deliverable report D4.1*. While the gratings written on flat substrates were only made for benchmarking purposes, the other two gratings were used in spectrometers:

1. A grating with variable line density (VLS) on a spherical substrate was designed for the experimental chamber MUSIX and used parasitically during a beam time at the free-electron laser FLASH, DESY just before the facility was shut down for more than a year due to ongoing upgrades.
2. A grating with variable line density (VLS) on a spherical substrate was designed for the high-throughput XES spectrometer at beamline ID32 at the ESRF-EBS synchrotron source.

Both gratings were made on silicon substrates procured from the company Pilz Optics, based on specifications resulting from the grating designs. The substrates were characterized by ex-situ metrology regarding slope error, micro-roughness and radius of curvature at HZB, the results have been presented in *deliverable report D4.3*. The following *deliverable report D4.4* reported on the production of the gratings.

As the test at FLASH needed to be scheduled before the FLASH shutdown in June 2024, grating 1 was installed and tested in the MUSIX spectrometer at the beamline before being coated. The coating will be applied later in order to increase the achievable signal.

Grating 2 for beamline ID32 at ESRF-EBS was coated with platinum as described in deliverable report D4.4. Characterizations in real spectrometers were performed in order to assess the performance of the gratings and in order to later be able to determine potential detrimental influences from the coating process.

Results on grating 1 from the FEL FLASH

The grating number 1 was installed in the MUSIX instrument at FLASH at DESY [1]. Fig. 1 shows the grating mounted on the adjustable holder for the MUSIX chamber just before mounting it into the spectrometer.

Figure 1: The first test grating mounted on the holder for the MUSIX spectrometer [1] just before the measurements at the FEL FLASH at DESY in Hamburg.

Due to constraints in accessing the facility before the shutdown for upgrades, the characterization of the grating has been performed on the new beamline FL23 [2] that had just been set up. The focussing of the beamline was adjusted in order to optimally serve the following experiment that required an X-ray spot size on the order of $50\mu\text{m}$. The grating design though was performed under the assumption of a significantly smaller spot size, such that the current setting negatively impacted the achievable energy resolution. Nevertheless, the experimental team was able to record so-called RIXS-maps (RIXS stands for resonant inelastic X-ray scattering and the maps are obtained by scanning the incident photon energy while measuring a spectrum for each energy) and are shown in Fig. 2. The different panels display different diffraction orders of the grating, showing the decrease in diffraction efficiency for higher orders alongside an increase in energy resolution. The maps show the expected features for a RIXS map excited around the Fe L-edge on a Fe metal sample: The elastic peak is found around 0 eV energy loss and is rather weak. Fluorescence becomes visible starting at the resonance energy of about 706 eV and then shifts on the energy loss scale in the same way as the incident energy increases.

The extracted energy resolution agrees with simulations for the given spot size. No significant artefacts have been observed in the spectra.

Figure 2: RIXS map obtained with the test grating number 1 at FLASH, excited around the Fe L-edge on a Fe thin film. The left panel shows the first diffraction order, the right panel the second.

Results on grating 1 from the optics beamline at BESSY

The grating prior to coating was quantitatively characterized in a test beamline, the optics beamline at BESSY II designed for characterizing optical elements at soft X-ray wavelengths. Different positions on the grating have been measured to investigate the uniformity of the optical area and a good agreement with expectations has been found across the grating. A first quantitative characterization has been the absolute measurement of the diffraction efficiency. This has been compared to simulations for the actual grating structure and good agreement has been found. The results are shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Efficiency measurements and calculations for grating 1.

In a further measurement step, the detector angle has been scanned at fixed incident angle in order to observe the different diffraction orders and identify additional artefacts which could appear in between the expected diffraction orders. Some small, but systematic artefacts have been found, but they appear to be below the level where they disturb actual measurements with the grating. Investigations of the origin are nevertheless ongoing. Results are shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Scan of the detector angle on grating 1. The expected diffraction orders are observed. Additional unexpected features are found that are four orders of magnitude smaller than the relevant structures and seem not to be detrimental for applications.

Results on grating 2 from the synchrotron ESRF

The second test grating has been installed in the high throughput spectrometer at the XMCD branch of beamline ID32 at the ESRF in Grenoble, France. A picture of the setup is shown in Fig. 5. On the left, one can identify the vacuum tank hosting the sample. The grating chamber is in the center of the picture, while the detector mounted on an extended arm is visible on the right.

Figure 5: The high throughput spectrometer at ESRF ID32.

In a first step, the elastic scattering of a sample has been studied, which gives a direct measure of the energy resolution and a potential diffuse background. First and second diffraction order have been compared to the performance of a traditionally produced reference grating from HZB. Results match qualitatively and quantitatively the expectations and are shown in Fig. 6. The good performance in terms of energy resolution speaks for a well-respected VLS law over the entire length of the grating, i.e. reliable writing of grating structures with a continuously varying groove period over the full length of the test grating (120 mm).

Figure 6: (a) Achievable energy resolution at 930 eV in first and second diffraction order of the new grating in comparison to a mechanically ruled grating in first order from HZB. Measurements were done in the same setup and the same experimental run, by laterally translating the grating stage to go from one grating to the other. The reference grating has higher line density, which allows to achieve better energy resolution for the same diffraction order. (b) Comparison of the achieved and expected energy resolution considering the different contributions to the resolution. We find a good quantitative agreement, confirming that the test grating performs as expected in terms of resolution.

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Figure 7: (a) Spectra from a Pr^{3+} test sample obtained at ESRF ID32. First and second grating orders of the new grating are used and compared to a mechanically ruled reference grating as before. Here, different normalization methods are applied in order to highlight resolution (peak widths, top), and grating efficiency (peak intensities after normalization to incident photon flux and grating length, bottom).

(b) Photon counts integrated over the full spectrum before and after normalization to 100 mm grating length. The reduced grating length of the test grating, 120 instead of 140 mm, should give a 15% lower total signal, whereas the reduced line density, 800 lines/mm instead of 1200 lines/mm, should enhance the diffraction efficiency by about 20% at 930 eV. One would therefore expect a very similar throughput for both gratings.

In a second step, a Pr^{3+} test sample was inserted and measured at the Pr M_5 edge (930 eV). The obtained spectra are again compared between first and second grating diffraction order and the mechanically ruled reference grating. In order to visualize differences in different ways, a set of normalization methods has been applied and the results are displayed in Fig. 7. The grating performance in terms of resolution is again as expected and very similar to the mechanically ruled reference grating. However, in terms of efficiency the grating deviates from the performance that one would expect based on its design parameters. The test and reference grating should have a very similar throughput in the first diffraction order. We find however that for the test grating the second order intensity is strongly enhanced at the expense of the desired first order diffraction efficiency. At a grazing incidence angle of about 1.7 degrees, where both diffraction orders could be brought into focus, we find very similar efficiency for both orders.

The explanation for the undesired enhancement of the 2nd and higher diffraction orders can be found in the groove shape measured by AFM along different parts of the grating. Fig. 8a shows AFM profiles of the grooves measured locally at the entrance, the centre and the exit side of

the test grating. At all three positions the groove shape deviates notably from the desired triangular shape.

In order to quantify the effect of the deviation in the groove shape from triangular, grating efficiency calculations for 930 eV using the CARPEM code (SOLEIL) were performed with the AFM profiles measured prior to coating as input. The results are shown in Fig. 8b and are in line with the experimental observations. A strong enhancement of the second order diffraction efficiency at the expense of the desired first order efficiency is observed. For an incidence angle of about 1.7 degree, we find the 1st and 2nd order grating efficiencies are exactly equal if we take the average over the 3 AFM profiles as representative of the full grating. Experimental verification of these calculations via further AFM measurements and measurements of the grating efficiency after Pt coating are under way at HZB.

Figure 8: (a) Groove profiles measured with AFM at three different positions of the grating, compared to the desired groove shape (0.75° blaze angle, 175° apex angle) and period. (b) Simulated grating efficiencies in first and second diffraction order for the ideal triangular groove profiles and the three groove profiles measured by AFM. The grating efficiency average over the three measured AFM profiles is shown in red.

Optical characterization of grating 2

Grating 2 was characterised before and after coating at the ESRF using microinterferometry (VEECO NT9800) which measures height variations on the grating surface with sub-Angstrom height resolution. These measurements revealed some subtle periodic artefacts in the ruled structures with periodicities significantly larger than the grating line spacing of $\sim 1.25 \mu\text{m}$:

- i. Long ($\approx 18.6 \text{ mm}$) period small ($0.2\text{-}0.3 \text{ nm}$) height steps along the grating length. Following Pt deposition these steps are also visible with the naked eye.
- ii. Intermediate ($\approx 38 \mu\text{m}$) period sawtooth like height profile variations with amplitude $\approx 0.35 \text{ nm}$ along the grating length.
- iii. Moderate (0.86 mm) period line structures across the grating width

These artefacts are shown in Figure 9. At the moment there is no indication that these features are performance limiting for the grating. The $38 \mu\text{m} \times 860 \mu\text{m}$ periodicities correspond to the dimensions of the mainfield dimensions used during the e-beam lithography. The origin of the 18.6 mm steps is, as yet, unclear.

Figure 9: Height defects observed on the surface of grating 2.

(Top) 18.6 mm period steps (yellow arrows) visible on grating.

(Middle) Microinterferometry measurement of the grating in the vicinity of one of the steps showing (i) the step, (ii) the $\sim 38 \mu\text{m}$ period sawtooth profiles and (iii) the $860 \mu\text{m}$ period horizontal lines (Colour scale blue-red: $\pm 1\text{nm}$).

(Bottom) Line profiles, before and after coating, extracted from microinterferometry measurements. The finely ($\sim 1.25 \mu\text{m}$) spaced grating lines which are superimposed on these features are beyond the lateral resolution limit of the instrument and hence not visible.

Summary and conclusion

The report describes the final technological deliverable of the LEAPS-Innov WP4. At-wavelength tests on the prototype gratings were performed at spectroscopy beamlines at an XFEL and a synchrotron source. In both cases, the gratings performed as expected regarding their spectral resolution and showed no significant flaws or artifacts in the obtained spectra.

Ex-situ analysis techniques revealed some deviations and artifacts of the grating structures. Slight periodic features were visible on grating 2, which stem from the electron-beam writing process. However, as these features were of sub-nanometer height, these did not have any detrimental effect on the performance of the device. AFM measurements on the line profile of grating 2 showed clear deviations from the desired profile, leading to a reduced diffraction efficiency compared to the theoretical values. Such deviations did not occur on the line profiles of grating 1, and their origin are presently unclear.

In spite of the line profile deviations of grating 2, the tests generally confirm that the novel fabrication technology of blazed gratings on curved substrates by electron-beam lithography works. It thus provides an alternative route to the conventional ruling technology, with the essential advantage that it provides additional flexibility regarding design and optical functionality.

References

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